

THE JAMES RIVER WALNUT

Probably Cross Between Butternut and English Walnut—Shows Remarkable Vigor, Although Productivity is Slight and Nuts of no Commercial Value—Promising as Bud Stock for Timber—Vigor of Root Stock Increased When Scions of Hybrid are Used.

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IN VIRGINIA, between Portsmouth and Richmond, on the south side of the James River, there is located the well-known and historical mansion of colonial days, "Lower Brandon." Across the river, just opposite "Lower Brandon" is "Rowe Farm", another of the old Virginia estates dating back to colonial days. On Rowe Farm there is growing one of the most remarkable walnut trees of which there is any record in this country.

The tree is of gigantic proportions, reaching a height of 100 feet, with its head, or crown of branches, towering above all other trees in the neighborhood. Its spread of branches was formerly 134 feet, but during a recent storm a large branch was broken off reducing its present spread of branches to 123 feet. At four feet from the ground the trunk of this tree measures 31 feet three inches in circumference, and at six feet from the ground, over 25 feet in circumference. At 12 feet from the ground the trunk divides into four large branches, three of which are larger than any tree in the neighborhood.

No one can tell how old this remarkable tree is, and there is no record to indicate its age. I am, however, informed that the old farm house on this place was built about 200 years ago and the supposition is that the seed or young tree from which this tree has developed, was planted at the same time. The size of the tree would lead one to believe that it is from 150 to 200 years old, and it also shows that the tree is of extraordinarily rapid growth,

which is no doubt due to its hybrid origin, for if its rate of growth were the same as that of our native walnut, it would have had to be planted before the settlement of Jamestown—1607—in order to have attained its present size.

I believe this tree to be a hybrid between our native butternut walnut (*Juglans cineria*) and the Persian, or so-called English, walnut (*Juglans regia*). The outer pericarp, or husk, of the fruit resembles our common black walnut (*Juglans nigra*). The nut also, in many respects, resembles *Juglans nigra*, but it is of larger size and of elongated shape. The habit of the tree, the growth of the branches, the bark and the leaves, which are composed of from five to seven pairs of leaflets, their shape, entire margins and veining, would indicate a very close relationship to the Persian Walnut (*Juglans regia*). The kernel of the nut is so small that it is not considered of any value for home use, and it certainly is of no commercial value as an edible nut.

Prof. C. S. Sargent, of the Arnold Arboretum, Jamaica Plains, Mass., who has seen trees similar to this one, is inclined to believe it to be a hybrid between *regia* and *nigra*. I, however, am lead to believe that it is a hybrid between *regia* and *cineria* for the following reasons:

The leaves of the hybrid have little pubescent hairs at the base of and along the veins of the leaflets that are entirely lacking in any other species I know of. The shape of the nut is more like *cineria* than *nigra*, and upon examining a cross-

THE JAMES RIVER WALNUT TREE.

Professor C. S. Sargent of the Arnold Arboretum, Boston, called this the most remarkable tree in the eastern United States. Vigor is its most marked characteristic—note its size in comparison with the horse and buggy underneath. There is good reason to believe that it is a hybrid, and Mr. Bisset finds strong evidence to show that it is a cross between the common butternut and the Persian or so-called English Walnut. (Figure 1.)

Persian Walnut (*J. regia*)
James River Hybrid Nut

Black Walnut (*J. nigra*)
Butternut (*J. cinerea*)

THE HYBRID AND ITS POSSIBLE PARENTS.

Merely from an inspection of the product, one is quite ready to admit that the Persian or English Walnut was one of its parents. The appearance of the nut itself does not give any safe indication as to whether the other parent was the black walnut or the closely allied butternut; but by a comparison of the leaves, and of the pubescence of bud-sticks, Mr. Bisset decides in favor of the latter. Second generation trees are now being grown, and as soon as their habit to bear the problem should be settled beyond dispute. (Figure 9)

section of the nut it appears as if the many fine lines, or divisions, of cineria had become solidified in the nut of the hybrid, thus causing the thick, hard shell of the seedling.

There is a young walnut tree growing a short distance from the old one (not over 150 yards away), which is said to have been raised from a seed borne by the old tree and planted about 1860. This is about the same height as the parent tree, and has a trunk about two and one-half feet in diameter. Its habit of growth, leaves, trunk, and bark are similar in every respect to that of the parent tree, with the single exception that the young twigs are heavily covered with pubescent hairs, which it would seem to have inherited from the butternut parent (*Juglans cineria*.)

Neither of the trees are prolific bearers, and what nuts they do bear seem to be of extremely low vitality, as so far we have not been able to learn of any other seedling trees being grown from them. The low vitality of the seeds indicates a weakness that is not at all uncommon in hybrids.

Professor Asa Gray was at one time shown young fruits from the old walnut tree, which he at once identified as *Juglans cineria*; the shape of the nuts being elongated and sharp-pointed, as in that species; but much wider or thicker. It is but just, however, to say that no leaves accompanied the specimen sent Professor Gray, to help him in his identification.

There is one character in the leaves of the old tree that resembles nigra, namely, that the leaflets have the sickle-like form of that species. Notwithstanding this leaflet resemblance however, and taking into consideration all of the characteristics of the old tree, and specially those of the young one (which, I think, we may be permitted to call the second generation) the shoots or young twigs of which have reverted to,

or developed, the pubescent hairs of cineria, I believe this walnut to be a cross between regia and cineria, as before stated.

Now as to the value of this tree and similar hybrids, many have feared that, owing to their rapidity of growth, there would be danger of the scion overlapping the stock, and a poor growth be obtained as a result. Experiments being carried on at the present time in California, in grafting hybrid walnuts on the native California Black, have shown that the scion of the hybrid stimulates the stock itself to a more rapid growth and, therefore, we may find that the rapidity of growth of the hybrids will present no difficulties to the successful propagation and utilization of these hybrids for lumber production.

The soil upon which these two trees are growing is an alluvial, rich, sandy loam, of great depth, a soil well suited to the best development of the walnut tree.

In spite of this evidence, some of my friends are inclined to doubt the hybrid origin of this tree and to think it probably an aberrant form of the English walnut, as it is a well known fact that this species presents many variations or forms which yield nuts with all kinds of shells varying from that of the paper-shell variety; that can be easily crushed between the fingers, to the hard, thick-shelled varieties that are used so extensively in Germany and Switzerland in making small toys—the toys being carved out of these nuts. If the nuts borne by this tree were of greater vitality we would soon be able to determine without a doubt the parentage of the tree, for the young seedlings would show in their leaf characters the usual variation of seedlings from hybrids, but owing to this low vitality of the seed, it will, I am afraid, be some time before we can definitely decide upon the parentage of the tree.